

Assessing Global Elevation Models for Mapping the Low Elevation Coastal Zone

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Abstract— Elevation data are critical for assessments of coastal hazards, including sea-level rise (SLR), flooding, storm surge, tsunami impacts, and wave run-up. Previous research has demonstrated that the quality of data used in elevation-based hazard assessments must be well documented and applied properly to assess potential impacts. Global digital elevation models (DEMs), at 30- to 90-meter resolution, have been used extensively to map and characterize coastal environments and the at-risk resources (population and built structures) contained therein. The inherent absolute vertical accuracy of global DEMs precludes their usefulness for assessing exposure to fine increments (< 1 meter) of coastal inundation at high confidence levels. However, global DEMs are highly suitable for delineation of the global low elevation coastal zone (LECZ) (elevation < 10 meters). An accuracy evaluation of global DEMs over the United States has been conducted to quantify their performance in correctly mapping the LECZ, namely in terms of vertical uncertainty and corresponding confidence levels for several representations of the coastal zone. The evaluation approach includes comparison of the DEMs with an extensive set of high-accuracy geodetic control points as the independent reference data covering a variety of coastal relief settings. The 1-arc-second (30-meter) global DEMs evaluated include ALOS World 3D, ASTER GDEM, Copernicus, FABDEM, and NASADEM, and the 3-arc-second (90-meter) global DEMs include CoastalDEM, Copernicus, MERIT, and TanDEM-X. Additionally, lower resolution (1-kilometer) global DEMs were also assessed, namely the Global Lidar Lowland DTM (derived from ICESat-2) and the GEDI 1-km DEM. The results of the accuracy characterization show that FABDEM performs the best (minimal vertical bias and lowest vertical root mean square error) for high-confidence mapping of the LECZ. Among 90-m DEMs, CoastalDEM performs best, although the differences across datasets are minimal. The results also demonstrate the importance of rigorously accounting for elevation uncertainty when applying global DEMs for coastal mapping applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the low-lying nature of many coastal lands, the topography, or elevation in relation to sea level, largely controls their exposure to adverse effects of increased water levels, both chronic conditions (sea-level rise) and episodic events (storm surge inundation or king tide flooding). Elevation data, notably in the form of digital elevation models (DEMs), are therefore critical for assessing exposure to permanent or temporary flooding and other effects of increased water levels along the coast.

Previous research has demonstrated that the quality of data used in elevation-based coastal hazard assessments must be well documented and applied properly to assess potential impacts [1][2]. The vertical uncertainty of the input elevation data substantially controls the minimum increments of inundation that can be effectively used in coastal hazard assessments. When properly characterized, the vertical accuracy of the DEM can be used to report assessment results with the uncertainty stated in terms of a specific confidence level.

Global DEMs, at 30- to 90-meter resolution, have been used extensively to map and characterize coastal environments and the at-risk resources (population and built structures) contained therein. However, in most cases, uncertainty has not been considered. An accuracy evaluation of global DEMs has been conducted to quantify their performance in mapping the global low elevation coastal zone (LECZ), namely in terms of vertical uncertainty and corresponding confidence levels for several delineations of the coastal zone.

II. DATA AND METHODS

A. Data

The 1-arc-second (30-meter) global DEMs evaluated include ALOS World 3D (AW3D30) [3], ASTER GDEM [4], Copernicus (COP30) [5], FABDEM [6], and NASADEM [7], and the 3-arc-second (90-meter) global DEMs include CoastalDEM [8], Copernicus (COP90) [5], MERIT [9], and TanDEM-X [10]. Additionally, lower resolution (1-kilometer) global DEMs were also assessed, namely the Global Lidar Lowland DTM (GLL DTM) (derived from ICESat-2) [11] and the GEDI 1-km DEM (https://daac.ornl.gov/GEDI/guides/GEDI_L3_LandSurface_Metrics_V2.html).

The global DEMs were assessed by comparison with an extensive set of high-accuracy geodetic control points as the independent reference data covering a variety of coastal relief settings in the conterminous United States (CONUS). The control points are a product of the U.S. National Geodetic Survey (NGS) and are known as “GPS on Bench Marks” (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/metadata/landing-page/bin/iso?id=gov.noaa.nodc:0209231>). These points are considered to be NGS’s best control points, with millimeter- to centimeter-level accuracies, used in development of hybrid geoid models, so they are an excellent reference dataset for comparing with DEMs for accuracy assessment purposes. The points have been used extensively for such analyses [12][13]. For the study area of the CONUS coast, a subset of 3,713 points (with elevation < 10 meters) were extracted from the full GPS on Bench Marks dataset of more than 37,000 points.

B. Methods

To calculate the absolute vertical accuracy for each global DEM, the elevation value at every reference point is compared to the corresponding DEM elevation (extracted via bilinear interpolation at the exact point location) and the difference in elevations is recorded. The difference represents the DEM error at that point. The differencing operation is done by subtracting the reference point elevation from the DEM elevation. In this way, the difference statistics from the point comparisons are easy to interpret; that is, a positive mean error indicates that on average the DEM is too high (the DEM has a positive bias). Conversely, a negative mean error indicates that on average the DEM is too low (a negative bias). Prior to comparison of the DEMs and the reference data, the control points were transformed to be in the same horizontal coordinate system and vertical reference frame (vertical datum) of each of the DEMs, so the difference statistics do not contain any artificial biases.

For inundation modeling, a specific case of coastal hazard assessment, the DEM is the base data on which the water level is raised to delineate the land area subject to inundation under the selected water level (i.e., areas with an elevation less than the

water level). Such a procedure is essentially an elevation contouring process whereby a line of constant elevation at the selected water level is derived from the elevation data. It is easy to define such an elevation contour, especially in a geographic information system, and the vertical increment between adjacent contours (or the contour interval) must be specified. A small interval can be applied to any DEM but doing so does not imply that the derived contours automatically meet published accuracy standards. The interval must not be so small that it falls within the bounds of vertical error of the DEM, as such an operation would place the measurement (elevation increment) “in the noise” of the underlying elevation data.

Based on the concept of elevation contour line accuracy, a method has been developed [1] to determine the minimum contour interval (or in the case of inundation modeling, the minimum increment of water level increase) that should be used to meet a specified confidence level. Using that minimum interval ensures that the contours are truly supported by the DEM given its inherent vertical uncertainty. In the United States, legacy national map accuracy standards applied to topographic contour maps specify that 90% of tested elevations should fall within one-half of the map contour interval [14], and this has been called the vertical map accuracy standard (VMAS) with a 90% confidence level, or alternatively “linear error at 90% confidence” (LE90). Based on the contour accuracy standard, it has been demonstrated [15] that the contour interval (CI) can be expressed directly as a factor of the elevation data accuracy, as in $CI = LE90 \times 2$. Two of the most commonly used DEM error metrics are root mean square error (RMSE) and LE95, and direct translations among RMSE, LE90, and LE95 are available [14], assuming the errors are from an unbiased normal distribution. Because the error metrics represent a portion of the cumulative probability distribution of errors, a confidence level can be stated for the minimum increment, for example 68% confidence for RMSE (equivalent to the “one sigma” error, or standard deviation of the errors for an unbiased normal distribution), 90% confidence for LE90, and 95% confidence for LE95.

By applying the concept of contour line accuracy, or alternatively, minimum inundation increment, (as a function of DEM accuracy), it has been documented that global DEMs are not suitable for modeling exposure to fine increments (< 1 meter) of coastal inundation at high confidence levels [15]. However, given their range of inherent vertical accuracy, global DEMs are suitable for general delineation of the LECZ (areas with elevations < 10 meters above sea level), a commonly used elevation threshold to delimit coastal zones [16][17][18]. The vertical accuracy statistics calculated in the accuracy assessment reported here are applied in the contour accuracy approach to quantify the performance of the free and open global DEMs for mapping the LECZ, including stating the confidence level.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the accuracy assessment are shown in Table I. The results are grouped by sets of rows for the 30-m DEMs (FABDEM, COP30, AW3D30, NASADEM, ASTER GDEM) (rows 2-6), 90-m DEMs (CoastalDEM, COP90, TanDEM-X, MERIT) (rows 7-10), and 1-km DEMs (GLL DTM, GEDI) (rows 11-12).

TABLE I. ACCURACY ASSESSMENT RESULTS

DEM	DEM grid spacing	No. of ref. points	Mean error (m)	RMSE (m)	Min. interval (m) at 68% conf.	Min. interval (m) at 95% conf.
FABDEM	30 m	3696	-0.055	1.231	2.463	4.827
COP30	30 m	3676	0.401	1.570	3.140	6.154
AW3D30	30 m	3578	1.029	2.809	5.617	11.010
NASADEM	30 m	3641	0.638	3.090	6.180	12.113
ASTER GDEM	30 m	3646	5.874	7.199	14.398	28.219
CoastalDEM	90 m	3696	-0.810	2.092	4.183	8.199
COP90	90 m	3678	0.786	2.110	4.221	8.273
TanDEM-X	90 m	3733	0.942	2.324	4.648	9.111
MERIT	90 m	3594	1.104	2.338	4.676	9.166
GLL DTM	1 km	2116	-0.734	1.528	3.056	5.990
GEDI	1 km	3099	-0.234	2.608	5.217	10.224

Among the 30-m DEMs, FABDEM performs the best, exhibiting the lowest vertical RMSE (1.23 m) and minimal vertical bias (about -6 cm). This translates into a contour interval of 2.46 m at 68% confidence, and a contour interval of 4.83 m at 95% confidence. Thus, FABDEM is very suitable for extremely high-confidence delineation of the LECZ (i.e., the 10-m contour). In fact, FABDEM could be used to delineate a 5-m “shoreline zone” at better than 95% confidence, and even a very low elevation coastal zone of 2.5 meters at 68% confidence. COP30 is also appropriate for very high-confidence mapping of the 10-m LECZ. AW3D30 and NASADEM could also be used for such LECZ delineation, albeit at lesser confidence levels. ASTER GDEM is not appropriate for accurate mapping of the LECZ.

Among the 90-m DEMs, CoastalDEM performs the best, although the performance differences across the 90-m DEMs is minimal. CoastalDEM, COP90, TanDEM-X, and MERIT are suitable for high-confidence mapping (better than 95% confidence) of the 10-m LECZ, and each could be used to delineate a 5-m shoreline zone at about 68% confidence. Although GLL DTM is at a much reduced spatial resolution of

1-km (compared to other global DEMs), this DEM is also found to be suitable for very high-confidence mapping of the 10-m LECZ.

It is important to note that the calculation of the minimum interval is based solely on the RMSE. In selection of a DEM for coastal zone mapping, users should also note the mean error (vertical bias) of the DEMs, which is fairly substantial in some cases. In terms of inundation modeling, the mean error can indicate whether use of the DEM will on average overpredict or underpredict areas subject to inundation.

IV. CONCLUSION

Numerous medium resolution global DEMs are available for regional, continental, and global coastal hazard assessment. Rigorous accuracy assessment of the DEMs provides quantitative information about which DEM could perform the best for high-confidence mapping of the global low elevation coastal zone. The results of the assessment reported here show that FABDEM is the most accurate and is quite well suited for high-confidence delineation of 5-m and 10-m coastal zones.

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